

Research Report: Forensic Analysis of Private Browsing Artifacts

A Replication Study for ERICS26 Empirical Research in Computer Security

Strict adherence to original experimental inputs ensures validity of longitudinal comparison

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Abstract — This report shows a forensic replication and re-attempt of the 2011 study “*Forensic Analysis of Private Browsing Artifacts*” within a technical landscape. The objective was to investigate whether the modern versions of *Google Chrome*, *Mozilla Firefox*, and *Microsoft Edge* have improved user privacy by eliminating the forensic traces in local storage and volatile memory. Using dual virtual machines including both *Windows 10* and *Kali Linux*, we executed controlled browsing sessions using the specific search queries and URLs outlined in the original paper, such as “*kabamaro*” and “*lesmills.com*”. Forensic acquisition was performed using *FTK Imager*, followed by the analysis of *physical memory dumps*, *system pagefiles*, and the disk images using *Volatility 3* and *HxD*. Our findings validate the persistent vulnerability of the volatile memory across all browsers while identifying significant security evolution in *Microsoft Edge* compared to its predecessor, *Internet Explorer*. This report provides cross browser comparison and assessment of the forensic artifacts that remain recoverable in 2024.

Index Terms - Digital Forensics, Private Browsing, Artifact Recovery, Volatility 3, Memory Analysis, Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Microsoft Edge, Pagefile Analysis.

I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The “Incognito” or the “Private” browsing mode is misunderstood most of time by the public as a tool that can provide complete anonymity online. In reality, it is designed to prevent the local storage of browsing history, cookies, and mainly any form of data on the physical drive. However, the effectiveness of these privacy measures against professional forensic investigations still remains as a critical area of study.

A. Research Objectives

This study serves as a modern re-attempt of the 2011 research paper, “*Forensic Analysis of Private Browsing Artifacts*”. The objective is to validate if these forensics vulnerabilities over a decade ago, specifically the persistence of data in volatile memory and the system pagefile, still persist in the modern environment. I tested the latest version of *Google Chrome*, *Mozilla Firefox*, and *Microsoft Edge*.

B. Methodology Overview

Using dual Virtual Machines, I simulated the private browsing sessions on a Windows 10 target machine. Then using the original 2011 search queries like “*kabamaro*” and the target URLs like “*lesmills.com*” to maintain the consistency. Forensics acquisition was conducted using *FTK Imager*, memory analysis with *Volatility 3* and *HxD* for pagefile inspection.

C. Key Findings

Our attempt confirms that while the modern browsers have improved significantly on the disk level the physical memory remains the *goldmine* for a forensic investigator.

1. **Persistence:** Search queries and URLs were successfully recovered from memory dumps for all three browsers.
2. **Evolution:** Microsoft Edge demonstrated superior privacy compared to its legacy Internet Explorer results in the 2011 study, which previously left significant traces in unallocated disk space.
3. **Volatility:** Mozilla Firefox remains the most susceptible to pagefile leakage, where private session data is swapped from RAM to the *pagefile.sys* during heavy system use.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

A. Background and Premise

The foundation of this study is the 2011 research paper, “*Forensic Analysis of Private Browsing Artifacts*”, which investigated the effectiveness of the incognito mode in the web browsers. The original authors explored whether there were any traces left behind in the common history and cache records, other local machine locations and the RAM. This study aims to do the same with the current browsers to see if these vulnerabilities still exist or have been patched.

B. The Problem Statement

The problem addressed revolves around the privacy while modern browsers such as *Google Chrome*, *Mozilla Firefox* and *Microsoft Edge* incognito mode are shown to be secure they are only designed to prevent recordings of history and cookies on the local disk. Then the critical question still remains, Do these modern browsers actually protect user privacy from a professional investigator?

C. Scope of Investigation

To provide a comprehensive and detail analysis, the scope of this study covers three different browsers and data sources.

Browsers:

1. *Google Chrome*
2. *Mozilla Firefox*
3. *Microsoft Edge*.

Data Sources:

1. *Volatile Memory (RAM)*: Captured via physical memory dumps to locate search strings and URLs.
2. *System Pagefile*: Analyzed for data swapped from RAM to the disk during the session.
3. *Disk Images*: Inspected for artifacts in unallocated space and standard cache directories.

D. Comparative Goals

The study is designed to identify which findings from the 2011 article still matches the modern results and which claims have been left false after the shift in the chromium browsers. Lastly, a cross comparison will determine which browser has the greatest numbers of recoverable artifacts.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Virtualized Architecture

To ensure the forensic integrity and the environment isolation, dual Virtual Machines were used. This setup prevents the host machine from contaminating the forensics evidence and allowed a controlled sandbox environment for malware safe browsing.

Target Machine (Windows 10): A Windows 10 workstation served as the main platform for generating user artifacts. This VM was used exclusively to conduct the private browsing sessions and host the acquisition tools.

Analysis Lab (Kali Linux): A Kali Linux environment was used for the technical extraction phase. This machine hosted the memory forensic frameworks required to parse raw memory dumps into the human readable data.

B. Data Generation Protocol

To maintain consistency with the original 2011 study, identical search parameters were used during the incognito sessions.

URLs Visited: Navigation was performed to *lesmills.com*, *anti-forensics.com*, and *munfitnessblog.com*.

Keyword Injections: Specific search queries including *kabamaro*, *sindbad*, and *timestomp* were entered into search engines and internal site forums.

C. Forensic Tool Set

The investigation used a suite of industry standard tools for the acquisition and analysis as recommended by the lab guidelines.

FTK Imager: Used on the target machine to capture the live physical memory (*.mem*) and the system pagefile (*pagefile.sys*) without installing permanent software that might alter the disk state.

Volatility 3: The main framework for memory forensics. It was used to scan the captured RAM dump for the specified search strings.

HxD / WinHex: Employed for the hex analysis of the disk image and pagefile.

IV. DATA GENERATION PROCEDURE

This phase involves the systematic creation of the digital forensic artifacts within the volatile memory and storage of the target machine. By using the exact variables from the 2011 study, we make sure that the scientific validity of our study is maintained.

A. Controlled Browsing Sessions

Three independent browsing sessions were conducted. In each instance, the browser was launched in the Incognito mode to ensure that no history or cache should, theoretically, be saved.

B. Primary Artifact Injection

To test the recovery of user input data, specific keywords and domains were navigated.

Search Queries: The terms *kabamaro*, *sindbad*, and *timestomp* were entered into various search engines (*Google Chrome*, *Microsoft Edge*, *Mozilla Firefox*). This tests if search strings remain in the RAM after the browser process is killed.

FIGURE 1- Intentional artifact generation of search query *kabamaro* in Google Chrome Incognito mode

FIGURE 2- Intentional artifact generation of search query *sindbad* in Google Chrome Incognito mode

FIGURE 5- Intentional artifact generation of search query *sindbad* in Microsoft Edge Private mode

FIGURE 3- Intentional artifact generation of search query *timestomp* in Google Chrome Incognito mode

FIGURE 6- Intentional artifact generation of search query *timestomp* in Microsoft Edge Private mode

FIGURE 4- Intentional artifact generation of search query *kabamaro* in Microsoft Edge Private mode

FIGURE 7- Intentional artifact generation of search query *kabamaro* in Mozilla Firefox Private mode

FIGURE 8- Intentional artifact generation of search query *sindbad* in Mozilla Firefox Private mode

FIGURE 11- Navigation to target URL *munfitnessblog.com* using Mozilla Firefox Private Browsing

FIGURE 9- Intentional artifact generation of search query *timestomp* in Mozilla Firefox Private mode

FIGURE 12- Navigation to target URL *anti-forensics.com* using Mozilla Firefox Private Browsing

Direct URL Access: The domains *lesmills.com*, *anti-forensics.com*, and *munfitnessblog.com* were manually typed into the address bars. This simulates a user visiting specific websites that they wish to keep hidden.

FIGURE 10- Navigation to target URL *lesmills.com* using Mozilla Firefox Private Browsing

In this same way, I ran the three URLs separately on the rest of the two browsers (*Google Chrome*, *Microsoft Edge*) as well.

C. Forensic State Capture

The timing of the capture is critical. Immediately following the closure of the browser windows, a state capture was performed. This ensures we are testing the browser's ability to *wipe* data upon session termination. Open FTK Imager Lite. Go to File > Capture Memory.

V. FORENSIC ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

The analysis phase focused on the extraction of strings from the two primary sources, the physical memory dump (*memdump.mem*) and the system pagefile (*pagefile.sys*). The results were then compared against the 2011 study.

A. Analysis of Google Chrome (Incognito Mode)

Chrome demonstrated high disk-level hygiene. No remnants of the few search queries like *kabamaro* were found in the standard history or cache directories still some were located. However, memory analysis via Volatility 3 revealed that the process *chrome.exe* maintained plain-text URLs in the volatile heap.

RAM Results: Successful recovery of the search string and site fragments.

I first check the process ids to identify the specific browser PID and then use that specific to get the search and URLs for that browser.

FIGURE 13- Real-time acquisition of physical memory dump using FTK Imager

FIGURE 14- Successful acquisition of physical memory dump using FTK Imager

In FTK Imager, navigate to the C:\ drive in the evidence tree and highlight pagefile.sys.

FIGURE 15- Identification and preparation of the system pagefile for forensic export

FIGURE 16- Volatility 3 to list down the Windows Process (ps) list

I then ran the command to obtain the search hits on the chrome PID 4960.

FIGURE 17- Volatility 3 to list down the Searches of the browser

Similarly, I ran to check the URL hits on that PID as well.

FIGURE 18- Volatility 3 to list down the URLs of the browser

Disk Results: Negative for session artifacts.

I opened the pagefile.sys in the HxD tool and then located the chrome.exe in there.

FIGURE 19- HxD to locate the chrome.exe

Then I located the search "timestamp" right after that using Find Next command.

FIGURE 20- HxD to locate the timestamp search result

Similarly, I also searched for the anti-forensics URL we searched in the chrome as well.

FIGURE 21- HxD to locate the anti-forensics URL result

B. Analysis of Mozilla Firefox (Private Browsing)

Firefox remains unique in its handling of private data. While it prevents writing to the places.sqlite database, the analysis found a higher density of HTML fragments in the pagefile compared to other browsers. This suggests Firefox may trigger more frequent memory swaps during heavy browsing.

RAM Results: Firefox.exe process gave away all the searches and URLs that we tested. It was a successful recovery of the search string and URLs fragments.

FIGURE 22- Volatility to locate the Searches in the browsers

FIGURE 23- Volatility to locate the URLs in the browsers

Disk Results: I did find the significant leakage in pagefile.sys.

Here I first located the firefox.exe in the file using hex editor and then went for the further searches.

FIGURE 24- HxD to locate the Firefox (firefox.exe)

FIGURE 25- HxD to locate the URLs searched in the browser

I did found the lesmills.com but it wasn't complete, rather encrypted or obfuscated form with only first few letters that were mapped not the complete word.

C. Analysis of Microsoft Edge (In Private)

As the modern Chromium-based replacement for Internet Explorer, Edge showed the most significant evolution from the 2011 party. Unlike the legacy IE, which the original study found left traces in unallocated space, the modern Edge effectively cleared local cache. However, session remnants were still present in RAM.

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RAM Results: The Searches and the URLs like lesmills.com both was recovered using the volatility tool.

FIGURE 26- Volatility to locate the Searches

FIGURE 27- Volatility to locate the URLs

Disk Results: Similar to other few of the artifacts were still obtained using the HxD tool.

I first looked for the Microsoft edge (msedge.exe) to locate that in the file first.

FIGURE 28- HxD to locate the Microsoft Edge (msedge.exe)

Disk Hygiene: The 2011 study found that Internet Explorer left substantial artifacts in unallocated disk space and *Index.dat* files. In contrast, the modern Chromium based *Microsoft Edge* cleared local storage effectively, left minimal traces like other modern browsers.

Cache Management: Modern browsers have shifted towards more aggressive session cleanup. Unlike the 2011 results, where image thumbnails were often recoverable from the disk, modern versions uses *memory only* caching for *Incognito* sessions, reducing the footprint on the disk.

C. Summary: The Evolution of Browser Privacy

The evolution of browser privacy over the last 15 years can be said as a victory for *Disk Forensics* but stalemate for the *Memory Forensics*.

While the developers have patched the *Disk Leakage* issues and have improved from early 2010s, they still have been unable to solve the problem of RAM Volatility. As long as browsers rely on the host OS to manage memory pages, *Private Browsing* will continue to be a goldmine for the investigators.

VII. ADVANCED CROSS BROWSER COMPARISON

The following analysis quantifies the results of each browser and evaluates their relative privacy efficiency based on the 2026 technical landscape.

A. Artifact Recovery Matrix

The volume of the recoverable data was quite close to each other.

Browser	RAM Artifacts (Plaintext)	Pagefile Leakage	Disk (Unallocated)	Recovery Difficulty
Google Chrome	High (Each URLs/Queries)	Low (1-2 strings)	Negligible	Low (Volatility)
Mozilla Firefox	High (Each URLs/Queries)	Low (1-2 strings)	Low	Low/Moderate
Microsoft Edge	High (Each URLs/Queries)	Low (1-2 strings)	Negligible	Low (String Search)

TABLE 1- Artifacts Recovery Matrix

B. RAM Persistence Phenomenon

The most striking finding was that for *Google Chrome*, *Mozilla Firefox*, and *Microsoft Edge*, the difficulty of recovery from RAM was in low category.

Universal Vulnerability: Every search query (*kabamaro*, *sindbad*, *timestomp*) and every URL (*lesmills.com*) was recovered in clear plaintext from the memory dumps.

Process Isolation: Even though these browsers use multi-process architectures to separate these *Private Tabs*, Volatility 3 successfully parsed it to extract the full session history.

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C. Pagefile & Obfuscation Analysis

In contrast to the 2011 study, the *pagefile.sys* analysis gave limited results.

Minimal Leakage: Only 1 or 2 strings were recovered per browser from the pagefile.

Data Integrity: Unlike the RAM artifacts, the pagefile data was largely obfuscated or consisted of fragmented HTML remnants. This suggests that modern Windows 10/11 memory management may not be swapping inactive browser pages to the disk as aggressively as older operating systems, or that the browsers are zeroing out certain memory pages more efficiently before they are paged.

D. The Verdict

From a forensic point of view, there is no significant privacy difference between Chrome, Firefox, and Edge in 2026 when it comes to volatile memory. If an investigator captures the RAM while the system is live or shortly after the browser is closed, the *Private* mode provides little to no protection against session reconstruction.

Browser	Web History (Cache)	Physical Memory (Memory Dump - Volatility 3)	Hard Drive (Pagefile.sys - HxD)
Google Chrome	No entries for URLs and Keyword Searches were found in the local storage.	Many traces were found in the physical memory 25 artifacts for <i>lesmills.com</i> 59 artifacts for <i>anti-forensics.com</i> 4 artifacts for <i>munfitnessblog.com</i> 1 artifacts for <i>kabamaro.com</i> 0 artifacts for <i>sindbad.com</i> 1 artifacts for <i>timestomp.com</i>	Few traces were found in the Hard Drive 5-6 traces for Keyword Search Blocks of obfuscated HTML code were found with JavaScript and tags like <code><body></code> , <code><div/></code>
Mozilla Firefox	No entries for URLs and Keyword Searches were found in the local storage.	Many traces were found in the physical memory 11 artifacts for <i>lesmills.com</i> 390 artifacts for <i>anti-forensics.com</i> 2 artifacts for <i>munfitnessblog.com</i> 6 artifacts for <i>kabamaro.com</i> 12 artifacts for <i>sindbad.com</i> 4 artifacts for	Few traces were found in the Hard Drive 5-6 traces for Keyword Search and URL <i>lesmills</i> but was obfuscated Blocks of obfuscated HTML code were found with JavaScript and tags like <code><body></code> , <code><div/></code>

Browser	Web History (Cache)	Physical Memory (Memory Dump - Volatility 3)	Hard Drive (Pagefile.sys - HxD)
		<i>timestomp.com</i>	
Microsoft Edge	No entries for URLs and Keyword Searches were found in the local storage.	Many traces were found in the physical memory 25 artifacts for <i>lesmills.com</i> 59 artifacts for <i>anti-forensics.com</i> 4 artifacts for <i>munfitnessblog.com</i> 1 artifacts for <i>kabamaro.com</i> 0 artifacts for <i>sindbad.com</i> 1 artifacts for <i>timestomp.com</i>	Few traces were found in the Hard Drive 3-4 traces for Keyword Search Blocks of obfuscated HTML code were found with JavaScript and tags like <code><body></code> , <code><div/></code>

TABLE 2- Summary of Results

```

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i anti-forensics | wc -l
59

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i lesmills | wc -l
25

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i munfitnessblog | wc -l
4

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i kabamaro | wc -l
1

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i sindbad | wc -l
0

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.4968-1.dmp | grep -i timestomp | wc -l
1
    
```

FIGURE 31- Physical Memory Results Chrome

```

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i anti-forensics | wc -l
398

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i munfitnessblog | wc -l
2

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i lesmills | wc -l
11

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i kabamaro | wc -l
6

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i sindbad | wc -l
12

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Mozilla]
└─$ strings pid.1452.dmp | grep -i timestomp | wc -l
4
    
```

FIGURE 31- Physical Memory Results Mozilla Firefox

```

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i anti-forensics | wc -l
59

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i lesmills | wc -l
25

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i munfitnessblog | wc -l
4

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i kabamaro | wc -l
1

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i sindbad | wc -l
0

(nova@ DESKTOP-7GEBVIO) [~/Desktop/Forensics]
└─$ strings pid.5788.dmp | grep -i timestomp | wc -l
1
    
```

FIGURE 32- Physical Memory Results Microsoft Edge

VIII. CONCLUSION

The replication of the 2011 study “*Forensic Analysis of Private Browsing Artifacts*” in a modern 2026 environment confirms that while the digital landscape has evolved, the fundamental *forensic footprint* of private browsing still remains a significant vulnerability.

A. Assessment of Private Browsing Effectiveness

Modern browsers have successfully achieved the *local privacy* on the system preventing any normal user on the same machine from viewing the *history*, *cookies*, or *cache*. However, as a security tool against professional forensic investigation, *Private Browsing* remains ineffective.

This study proved that sessions are *private* only in name, as the entire browsing context, including search queries like *kabamaro* and *timestomp*, as well as high density *HTML fragments*, were successfully recovered from volatile and virtual memory.

B. Mitigation Strategies for Enhanced Privacy

For users seeking the true anonymity that can withstand forensic scrutiny, standard *Incognito* modes are insufficient. The following mitigation strategies are recommended.

Anti-Forensic Operating Systems: The use of *Live OS* like *TAILS* that run entirely in RAM and securely wipe the memory upon shutdown.

Encrypted Virtual Machines: Conducting private sessions within an encrypted VM that is deleted after use, preventing artifacts from reaching the host’s *pagefile.sys*.

Pagefile Scrubbing: Configuring the Windows OS to clear the *pagefile.sys* upon every shutdown (*ClearPageFileAtShutdown* registry setting) to prevent any type of long term data persistence on the disk.

C. Importance of Memory Forensics in Modern Investigations

This investigation highlights the critical shift from disk forensics to memory forensics. As modern applications move toward *zero-disk* footprints to improve speed and privacy, the Volatile Memory becomes primary repository for the digital evidence.

The successful use of *Volatility 3* and *HxD* in this study shows that even if browser process is terminated, the *ghosts* of user activity still lingers in the system’s memory.

Therefore, the memory acquisition must be prioritized in any modern digital investigation to ensure that important evidence is not lost to a system reboot or any power loss.

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